

STRENGTH EVALUATION OF NATURAL FIBERS WITH VARIATION OF WITHIN-FIBER CROSS-SECTIONAL AREA

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SUMMARY

Cross-sectional area of natural fibers is often evaluated as a circle by measuring a projection width of the fibers. Such uncertain evaluation often brings a significant error in strength evaluation. Thus we developed a new method of evaluating more correctly the fiber cross-sectional area, called 'DB-based approximation' method.

Keywords: Green composites, Natural fibers, Tensile strength, Cross-sectional area, Stochastic process

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, natural fiber reinforced composites [1] are expected as structural materials, and already applied to industrial products such as car interior parts and electrical products. Natural fiber made from plants mainly consists of cellulose, which has a high elastic modulus of 138GPa in its crystal [2]. Then it is expected that the natural fiber will widely be substituted for conventional glass fibers. In general, plant-based natural fibers have a large variation in cross-sectional area. However, the fiber cross-sectional area is often evaluated as a circle by measuring a projection width of the fiber. Such uncertain evaluation for the cross-sectional area often brings a significant error at the strength evaluation. In this study, we thus developed a new method of evaluating relatively correctly the fiber cross-sectional area, called 'DB-based approximation' method [3]. This DB-based approximation method is based on the database for a distribution of actual fiber cross-sectional area obtained from cross-sectional pictorial images of fiber-reinforced composites. The results showed that the proposed method is in a good agreement with real cross-sectional areas of curaua fibers [3], which is used as reinforcement of the composites. In order to establish the validity of DB-based approximation method, we applied this method to the cross-sectional area evaluation for kenaf and bamboo fibers. Moreover, a stochastic strength model based on Weibull probability considering the variation in cross-sectional area was newly proposed. Using this model, the effect of the variation in within-fiber cross-sectional area on the fiber strength was discussed through a Monte-Carlo simulation.

2 DB-BASED APPROXIMATION METHOD USING POLYGONAL ASSUMPTION

As mentioned above, usually the fiber cross-sectional area is calculated assuming a projection width as a diameter, which is measured by optical microscope or laser system. Figure 1 shows a microphotograph of the cross-section of a curaua fiber

reinforced biodegradable resin matrix composite. As easily known, the shape of the fiber cross-section is not circle. In this study, actual fiber cross-sectional area of curaua, kenaf and bamboo fibers, as indicated in painted area in black, were measured through an image analysis. The numbers of measurements for curaua, kenaf and bamboo fibers were 328, 312 and 301, respectively. At each images, the projective widths from twelve directions of 0 to 165 degrees were measured as shown in Figure 1. Then, the cross-sectional area of the fiber was evaluated by assuming the shape of icosi-tetragon (24-sided figure), composed of twelve disagonal lines equalized to twelve projective widths. Moreover, the actual cross-sectional area was also measured by the image data processing. The relations between the actual cross-sectional area and the circle and polygon-assumed areas for curaua, kenaf and bamboo fiber are shown in Figures 2, 3 and 4, respectively. It is proved that any correlation of the polygon-assumption area to the actual cross-sectional area is stronger than that of the circle-assumption area. The actual cross-sectional areas, the polygon-assumption cross-sectional areas, the coefficients of correlation and the approximate expressions for curaua, kenaf and bamboo fibers are shown in Table 1. From this table, it is expected that more exact cross-section area of natural fibers can be evaluated through polygon-assumption areas because these coefficients of correlation are higher. Thus, we proposed a new method of cross-sectional area measurement, based on the database (DB) of actual cross-sectional areas. This is denoted as DB-based approximation.

(a) Micrograph of cross-sectional area

(b) Polygon approximation

Figure 1 Optical micrograph of cross-section on a curaua fiber-reinforced composite and the assumption of cross-sectional shape.

(a) Circle-assumption

(b) Polygon-assumption

Figure 2 Relationship of actual cross-sectional area with (a) circle-assumption area, and (b) polygon-assumption area for curaua fibers.

Figure 3 Relationship of actual cross-sectional area with (a) circle-assumption area, and (b) polygon-assumption area for kenaf fibers.

Figure 4 Relationship of actual cross-sectional area with (a) circle-assumption area, and (b) polygon-assumption area for bamboo fibers.

Table 1 Correlation of actual cross-sectional area with circle- and polygon-assumption areas.

Fiber	Cross-sectional area [μm^2]			Coefficient of correlation		approximation
	Actual	Circle assumption	Polygon assumption	Circle assumption	Polygon assumption	
Curaua	5267	6696	6563	0.840	0.963	$y=0.637x+835$
Kenaf	5010	7356	6865	0.800	0.909	$y=0.606x+852$
Bamboo	9106	14541	13976	0.884	0.915	$y=0.498x+2153$

3 NATURAL FIBER STRENGTH MEASUREMENTS

The single fiber specimens with gauge length of 10 mm were prepared in order to measure the fiber strengths. The numbers of specimens for curaua, kenaf and bamboo fibers were 74, 36 and 40, respectively. The projective width of these natural fibers were consecutively measured from twelve directions of 0 to 165 degrees at 0.1 mm interval along their axial direction, using a lasar scan micro-meter (LSM-500S, Mitutoyo Corporation). In this case the shape of cross-section is assumed as an icosi-tetragon. Using these specimens, the quasi-static tensile tests were carried out at 0.8 mm/min. The average values of the measured cross-sectional areas and the tensile strengths are shown in Table 2. In this table, the reduced cross-sectional areas using the

approximate expressions in Table 1 are also shown. It is presumed that these tensile strengths (approximations in Table 2) are close to exact values because their cross-sectional areas are evaluated based on the DB-based approximation as mentioned above.

Table 2 Cross-sectional area and tensile strength calculated from polygon-assumption cross-sections.

Fiber	Cross-sectional area [μm^2]		Tensile strength [MPa]	
	Measurement	Approximation	Measurement	Approximation
Curaua	6176	4770	560.4	708.3
Kenaf	6599	4848	237.2	308.3
Bamboo	12111	8178	327.7	476.4

4 STATISTICAL MODELS BASED ON WEIBULL DISTRIBUTION

In this chapter, a new truncated cone model to estimate the tensile strength of natural fibers is proposed based on the stepped bar model [4], in order to depict the variation in within-fiber cross-sectional area more precisely. The conventional Weibull model, the stepped bar model and new truncated cone model are describe as below.

4.1 Conventional Weibull model

The artificial fibers such as carbon and glass fibers have almost a constant diameter and the shape of cross-section along their axial direction is uniform. In the case of these fibers, the conventional Weibull model has generally been applied to estimate the strength distributions. The conventional Weibull model, denoted as the straight bar model, is shown in Fig. 5, and the cumulative probability of fiber failure F is given by the following equation.

Figure 5 Straight bar model.

$$F = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{V}{V_0}\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right] = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\bar{A}}{A_0} \cdot \frac{L}{L_0}\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right] \quad (1)$$

Where m and σ_0 are Weibull shape and scale parameters in the case of gauge volume, area and length are V_0 , A_0 and L_0 , respectively. \bar{A} is the average cross-sectional area of a specimen, and $\bar{\sigma}$ is an average failure stress, which is defined as the failure load divided by \bar{A} . By transforming each side of Eq. (1) into logarithm, it is given as:

$$\ln \ln\left(\frac{1}{1-F_i}\right) - \ln\left(\frac{\bar{A}}{A_0}\right) - \ln\left(\frac{L}{L_0}\right) = m \cdot \ln \bar{\sigma}_i - m \cdot \ln \sigma_0 \quad (2)$$

Where $i=1,2,\dots,N$ and N is the number of fibers.

4.2 Stepped bar model

The stepped bar model is shown in Fig. 6. This model consists of n cylinder elements which have different average area A_j ($j=1\sim n$) and a constant length of Δx .

Figure 6 Stepped bar model.

The cumulative probability F_j of the fiber failure stress for j -th element in a fiber is given by the following equation.

$$F_j = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{V_j}{V_0} \left(\frac{\sigma_j}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right] = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{A_j \cdot \Delta x}{A_0 \cdot L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma_j}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right] \quad (3)$$

Where $V_j = A_j \cdot \Delta x$. Based on the Weakest link model, the failure probability of the fiber is given as:

$$F = 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - F_j) = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\Delta x}{L_0} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{\bar{A}_j}{A_0}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_j}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right] \quad (4)$$

To compare Eq. (4) with Eq. (1), the stress σ_j is rewritten as:

$$\sigma_j = \frac{P_i}{A_j} = \frac{\bar{A}}{A_j} \cdot \bar{\sigma} \quad (5)$$

In the case of $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$ considering the continuum cross-sectional variation, Eq. (4) is expressed as:

$$F = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\bar{A}}{A_0} \cdot \frac{L}{L_0} \cdot \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_0}\right)^m \cdot \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L \left(\frac{\bar{A}}{A(x)}\right)^{m-1} dx\right] \quad (6)$$

Where $A(x)$ is a stochastic process which expresses randomness of the within-fiber cross-sectional area along its axial direction. In the case of a uniform cross-sectional area, i.e. $A(x) = \bar{A}$, Eq. (6) coincides with Eq. (1). On the other hand, the failure probability of the fiber is rewritten as Eq. (7), when the change in cross-sectional area is discretely measured along the fiber axial direction.

$$F = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\bar{A}}{A_0} \cdot \frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_0}\right)^m \cdot R_1\right], \quad R_1 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{\bar{A}}{A_j}\right)^{m-1} \quad (7)$$

Where R_1 is a new parameter which expresses the variation in within-fiber cross-sectional area. By transforming each side of Eq. (7) into logarithm, it is given as:

$$\ln \ln\left(\frac{1}{1 - F_i}\right) - \ln\left(\frac{\bar{A}}{A_0}\right) - \ln\left(\frac{L}{L_0}\right) - \ln R_1 = m \cdot \ln \bar{\sigma}_i - m \cdot \ln \sigma_0 \quad (8)$$

The average strength $\bar{\sigma}_F$ of Eq. (7) is given as:

$$\overline{\sigma}_F = \sigma_0 \cdot \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\overline{A}}{A_0} \cdot \frac{L}{L_0}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \cdot R_1^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (9)$$

4.3 Truncated cone model

The truncated cone model is shown in Fig. 7. This model consists of n cone elements which have different average area \overline{A}_j ($j=1\sim n$) and a constant length of Δx . The failure probability of the fiber is also defined as Eq. (4).

Figure 7 Chains of circular truncated cone model.

The average area of j th element \overline{A}_j is defined as follows.

$$\overline{A}_j = \sqrt{A_j \cdot A_{j+1}} \quad (10)$$

The average strength of j th element σ_j is given as:

$$\sigma_j = \frac{P_i}{A_j} = \frac{\overline{A}}{A_j} \cdot \overline{\sigma} = \frac{\overline{A}}{\sqrt{A_j \cdot A_{j+1}}} \cdot \overline{\sigma} \quad (11)$$

By substituting Eq. (11) into Eq. (4),

$$\begin{aligned} F &= 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\overline{A}}{A_0} \frac{\Delta x}{L_0} \left(\frac{\overline{\sigma}}{\sigma_0}\right)^m \cdot \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{\overline{A}}{\sqrt{A_j \cdot A_{j+1}}}\right)^{m-1}\right] \\ &= 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\overline{A}}{A_0} \cdot \frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{\overline{\sigma}}{\sigma_0}\right)^m \cdot R_2\right], \quad R_2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{\overline{A}}{\sqrt{A_j \cdot A_{j+1}}}\right)^{m-1} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

By transforming each side of Eq. (12) into logarithm, it is given as:

$$\ln \ln\left(\frac{1}{1-F_i}\right) - \ln\left(\frac{\overline{A}}{A_0}\right) - \ln\left(\frac{L}{L_0}\right) - \ln R_{2i} = m \cdot \ln \overline{\sigma}_i - m \cdot \ln \sigma_0 \quad (13)$$

The average strength $\overline{\sigma}_F$ of Eq. (12) is given as:

$$\overline{\sigma}_F = \sigma_0 \cdot \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\overline{A}}{A_0} \cdot \frac{L}{L_0}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \cdot R_2^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (14)$$

4.4 Estimation of Weibull parameters

The experimentally obtained fiber strength data were applied to the straight bar, stepped bar and truncated cone models, in order to estimate the Weibull shape parameter m and scale parameter σ_0 . In this study m and σ_0 were respectively calculated as the gradient and intercept, by assuming the plotted distribution as a linear

approximation, in which all the left side and $\ln \bar{\sigma}_i$ of the right side of Eqs. (2), (8) and (13) are taken as Y -axis and X -axis, respectively. The cumulative failure probability $F_j = j/(N+1)$ is given by the mean rank method. Here, the estimation method of m was conducted as follows. First, m included in R_1 and R_2 was assigned as a default value, and the new one m' is then calculated through the least-squares method using m . The optimum value of m is defined as final value through some iteration in the convergence condition of $|m - m'| < 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$. The estimated results for Weibull shape and scale parameters of the natural fibers are shown in Table 3. In this table, it was found that the shape parameters obtained from the stepped bar and truncated cone models are larger than that obtained from the straight bar model. The reason why the strengths were larger and the scatters are smaller than that of the straight bar model is *exclusion* of the variation in within-fiber cross-sectional area, which can be achieved by setting the new parameter of R_1 or R_2 . The average strengths $\bar{\sigma}_F$ of the fiber using the stepped bar and truncated cone models were smaller than that using the straight bar model. It can be seen that the average strength decreases with increasing the scatter of the cross-sectional area on each element of the stepped bar and truncated cone models, because $R_i^{-1/m}$ ($i=1, 2$) in Eqs. (9) and (14) decreases as R_i increases. Furthermore, it was clarified from the estimated parameters that the stepped bar model has stronger sensitivity due to the change in cross-sectional area than the truncated cone model.

Table 3 Weibull parameters and average strengths.

Fiber	Weibull model	m	σ_0 [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}_F$ [MPa]	\bar{R}
Curaua	Straight bar	3.93	779	705	-
	Stepped bar	3.95	787	704	1.05
	Truncated cone	3.95	785	705	1.04
Kenaf	Straight bar	7.03	324	303	-
	Stepped bar	7.52	332	301	1.30
	Truncated cone	7.46	331	302	1.24
Bamboo	Straight bar	2.44	560	497	-
	Stepped bar	2.49	571	494	1.06
	Truncated cone	2.47	568	495	1.04

5 MONTE CARLO SIMULATION

In order to investigate the effect of the change in cross-sectional area of the fibers on the Weibull parameters and the average strength, a Monte Carlo simulation was conducted. In this simulation, we assumed the followings:

- (1) The average value for with-in fiber cross-sectional area of i -th fiber $E_i[A_{i,j}]$ is given by a normal distribution.
- (2) The coefficient of variation for with-in fiber cross-sectional area of i -th fiber CV_{Ai} is obeyed by a logarithmic normal distribution.
- (3) CV_{Ai} is independent on $E_i[A_{i,j}]$.
- (4) The j -th within-fiber cross-sectional area of i -th fiber $A_{i,j}$ is assigned using a normal distribution based on $E_i[A_{i,j}]$ and CV_{Ai} .
- (5) The strength of i -th fiber is obeyed by Weibull distribution.

5.1 Fiber assignment

In this section, 250 virtual curaua fibers considering the variational within-fiber cross-sectional area and strength along the fiber axial direction were assigned by following procedures.

- (1) 250 average cross-sectional areas $E_i^{vir}[A_{i,j}]$ were assigned through 250 normal random numbers subjected to the average value of the average area for with-in fiber cross-sectional area of N -th fiber $E^{vir}[E_i]=4770 \mu\text{m}^2$ and the coefficient of variation $CV_{E_i}^{vir}=53.12\%$.
- (2) 250 coefficient of variation for the cross-sectional area $CV_{A_i}^{vir}$ were assigned through 250 logarithmic normal random numbers subjected to the average value of the average coefficient for with-in fiber cross-sectional area of N -th fiber $E^{vir}[CV_{A_i}]=8.7\%$ and the coefficient of variation $CV_{CV_{A_i}}=70.1\%$.
- (3) After the random selection of combination between obtained average areas $E_i^{vir}[A_{i,j}]$ and coefficients $CV_{A_i}^{vir}$ were implemented, 81 cross-sectional areas of j -th element with $\Delta x=0.1$ mm in i -th fiber $A_{i,j}$ were assigned by 81 normal random numbers subjected to the $E_i^{vir}[A_{i,j}]$ and the standard deviation calculated by the combination.
- (4) The strength of j -th element in i -th fiber $\sigma_{i,j}$ was given by following equation based on Eq. (1) using a random number F_j in the range of (0, 1) as the cumulative failure probability.

$$\sigma_{i,j} = \sigma_{0i} \left(\frac{A_0 \cdot L_0}{A_{i,j} \cdot \Delta x} \ln \frac{1}{1 - F_j} \right)^{1/m_i} \quad (15)$$

Where m_i and σ_{0i} are the shape and scale parameters of i -th fiber. These are fitting parameters to correspond with the calculations to the experimental results about the shape parameter m and scale parameter σ_0 of fibers. Consequently, $m_i=4.000$ and $\sigma_{0i}=2250$ MPa in this simulation.

- (5) The minimum load $P_{i,min}$ of the failure load P_i calculated from the combination between $\sigma_{i,j}$ and $A_{i,j}$ was assumed as the failure load of i -th fiber. Then, the average strength of i -th fiber $\overline{\sigma}_i^{vir}$ was calculated using the $E_i^{vir}[A_{i,j}]$ and $P_{i,min}$.

5.2 Simulated results

The simulated results of Weibull parameters using the straight bar, stepped bar and truncated cone models are shown in Table 4. In this table, the average estimates of 50 simulations are shown. It was found that these results relatively agree with the experimental results in Table 3. That is to say, the validity of these simulations is established.

Table 4 Weibull parameters and average strengths by simulation.

Model	m	σ_0 [MPa]	$\overline{\sigma}_F$ [MPa]	R
Straight bar	4.04	763	690	-
Stepped bar	4.08	779	683	1.14
Truncated cone	4.05	771	689	1.05

5.3 Relation between variation of within-fiber cross-sectional area and Weibull parameters

To clarify the relation between the variation in cross-sectional area and Weibull parameters, the average coefficient of variation of the cross-sectional area $E[CV_{A_i}]$ was changed. Here, $CV_{CV_{A_i}}$ is a constant as 70.1[%]. The simulated Weibull parameters are shown in Figs. 8(a) and (b), in which these parameters are normalized by dividing the values simulated from the stepped bar or truncated cone models by those from the straight bar model, respectively. From these figures, it was found that m and σ_0 increase slightly with an increase in $E[CV_{A_i}]$, while the normalized average strength $\overline{\sigma_f}$ decreases largely, especially from $E[CV_{A_i}] = 12\%$ or 14% . This means, the straight bar model, i.e. the conventional Weibull distribution, has a possibility to bring some error to statistical strength evaluation of natural fibers, in case $E[CV_{A_i}]$ is given as 12% or more. In the present study, that of curaua fibers was measured as 8.7%, as mentioned above, and kenaf and bamboo fibers were measured as 10.8% and 16.7%, respectively. Thus, we can say that the proposed models may be applied to statistical strength evaluation of natural fibers.

In this study, on the other hand, compatibility of the stepped bar model or truncated cone model fitting better to the strength evaluation of natural fibers has not been discussed. The argument regarding best fitting model is a future work.

(a) Stepped bar to straight bar

(b) Truncated cone to straight

Figure 8 Ratio of Weibull parameters between two Weibull models.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In order to establish the validity of DB-based approximation method, we applied this method to the cross-sectional area evaluation of curaua, kenaf and bamboo fibers. Moreover, a stochastic strength model based on Weibull probability considering the variation in cross-sectional area was newly proposed. Using this model, a Monte-Carlo simulation for evaluating its validity was conducted. Consequently, the proposed models are more adaptable to the statistical strength evaluation than conventional model in some natural fibers which have a relatively large variation in cross-sectional areas.

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